

Acknowledgement

We wish to express our thanks to Dr. S. S. Gupta, Principal, D. S. College, Aligarh for providing the requisite facilities and Agra University, Agra for JRF (UGC) to one of them (U.K.R.).

References

1. S. N. PODDAR, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, **26**, 153; 1964, **27**, 67.
2. D. B. INGLE and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 609 and 103.
3. M. DESAI, B. M. DESAI, B. S. PATWARI and M. H. GANDHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 369.
4. U. K. RATHI, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University, Agra.
5. Y. K. REDDY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1965, **7A**, 368.
6. N. A. RAJU and K. NEELKANTAM, *Curr. Sci.* 1950, **19**, 383.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, 3rd Ed., 1968.
8. V. SESHAGIRI and S. BRAHAMJI, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **262**, 275.
9. G. LIPTAY, E. M. PAPP and K. BURGERS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 247.
10. C. DUVAL, "Inorganic Thermogravimetric Analysis", Elsevier London, 1953, pp. 236, 259 and 347.

Chalcones XXIV : Studies on Chalcone Complexes of Fe(III) and Cr(III)

SHYAM SUNDAR MISRA, P. C. DWIVEDI*, R. K.

UPADHYAYA **, V. P. SINGH † and D. R. GUPTA ††

Department of Chemistry, Feroz Gandhi College,
Rae Bareilly-229 001

Manuscript received 9 August 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

THE chalcones and their analogues are well known as multiprotecting agents +1-3. The field of coordination chemistry of these compounds has not been investigated widely⁴. However, 2-hydroxy chalcones are found⁵⁻⁷ useful as gravimetric reagents for various cations. It is, therefore, thought worthwhile to undertake the synthesis, isolation and study of a few 3-d transition metal cation complexes, i.e., Fe(III) and Cr(III) with 8-hydroxy-5-quinolinyl chalcone. The complexes were prepared at an ionic strength of 0.005 mole in 90% aqueous methanol at boiling water temperature. The spectrophotometric and conductometric studies evaluated the stoichiometry of the complexes. The molecular conductance measurements were made

* Chemistry Department, H. B. T. I., Kanpur-208 002.

** Chemistry Department, University of Alfatsh, Tripoli, (Libya).

† Chemistry Department, NREC College, Khurja, 203 131.

†† Chemistry Department, GBPUAT, PANTNAGAR, (U. P.) India.

with a view to study their stereochemistry. The characterisation of the complexes was done by elemental analysis. The I.R. spectra of the ligand 8-hydroxy-5-quinolinyl chalcone explores the possibility of chelation at $-OH$, $>C=O$ and $-C\equiv N$ groups.

Experimental

The solutions of metal nitrate of required strength were prepared in 90% aqueous methanol (v/v) of A.R. grade. The ligand 8-hydroxy-5-quinolinyl chalcone was obtained as reported⁷ and purified by repeated crystallisations and its homogeneity was checked by T.L.C. Spectrophotometric studies were made by Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20. Conductometric measurements were made with Toshniwal's conductivity bridge.

I.R. spectra was recorded in mujolmull with Beckmann spectrophotometer to study various important bands and the Gouy balance was used for the magnetic measurements. On the basis of spectrophotometric and conductometric results the stoichiometry of the complexes were found to be 1 : 3 metal ligand system. Double distilled water over alkaline potassium permanganate was used throughout the investigation and all the measurements were made at room temperature.

Isolation of the complexes :

The complexes were isolated by adding ligand solution to a hot methanolic solution of metal nitrates in the stoichiometric ratio of 3 : 1. The resulting dark coloured mixture was kept at about 50-60° over water bath with reflux condenser for about three hours, cooled filtered and the complex washed several times with cold absolute ethanol and finally recrystallised from dioxane.

Analysis :

Elemental analysis was performed by C.D.R.I., Lucknow and the metal components were determined gravimetrically⁸. The results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titration gave the stoichiometric ratio of the ligand to metal as 3 : 1. The molar composition of the complexes were further determined by mole-ratio method and confirmed by their elemental analysis.

The magnetic measurements of Fe(III) and Cr(III) complexes were carried out at 303°K by Gouy method and the μ_{eff} values were found to be 1.37 and 1.01 BM respectively indicates the formation of high ligand field, low spin octahedral

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	Carbon%		Hydrogen%		Nitrogen%		Metal%	
			Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found
1.	$\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$	Blue	73.82	74.20	4.10	4.00	4.78	4.93	6.37	6.58
2.	$\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$	Dark blue	74.14	74.86	4.12	4.21	4.80	5.19	5.94	5.73

complexes with d^5 and d^3 systems having one unpaired electron only.

The molar conductance (ΔM) values of the Fe(III) and Cr(III) complexes in dioxane was found to be 1.4 and 1.8 mhos respectively shows the non-electrolytic nature of the chelates. I. R. spectral data reveals that the lowering in $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequencies at 3250 and 1665 cm^{-1} of parent ligand on complexation. This lowering indicates the participation of these groups in co-ordination. $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group being at remoter position does not participate in the metal ligand interaction because the band corresponding to $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups remains unperturbed during chelation. New bands appear in the ligand complexes with Fe(III) at 345 cm^{-1} and 436 cm^{-1} whereas in Cr(III) at 285 cm^{-1} and 423 cm^{-1} respectively fairly attributable to metal-oxygen and metal-nitrogen bonds which is in accordance with the results of Poddar and Das⁹.

Taking into accounts the above results, most probable formula assigned to the complexes are.

$\text{M}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ where $\text{M} = \text{Fe}(\text{III})$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{III})$. Above structure satisfies maximum co-ordination number six for Fe(III) and Cr(III).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to authorities of H.B.T.I., Kanpur and C.D.R.I., Lucknow for providing necessary help and Dr. S. K. Sinha, Principal F. G. College for his keen interest.

References

1. K. K. HSU and F. C. CHEN, *Taiwan K. Hsue'h*, 1975, **27**, 236.
2. S. S. MISRA, *Chinese Chemical Soc.*, 1977, **24**, 45.
3. S. S. MISRA and D. R. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 412.
4. R. R. NAIDU, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 614.
5. K. S. SUNDAR, *Curr. Sci.*, 1965, **34**, 18.
6. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1020.
7. S. S. MISRA and BHOLA NATH, *Indian J. App. Chem.*, 1971, **4**, 260.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Logemann Group Ltd., London, 1969.
9. S. N. PODDAR and V. S. DAS, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 1105.

Application of Radius Ratio Criterion to the Stability of Pyrochlore in Some Mixed Metal Oxide Systems

V. S. DARSHANE

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Institute of Science, Bombay-400 032

Manuscript received 21 August 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

LITERATURE survey revealed that very little work is reported on pyrochlores where substitution of cations is carried out at A as well as B sites. Analysis¹ of natural pyrochlore minerals suggest that wide variety of both cationic and anionic substitutions are possible. Therefore, the systems $\text{Y}_{2-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{Ti}_{2-y}\text{Nb}_y\text{O}_7$, $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{Zr}_{2-y}\text{Nb}_y\text{O}_7$ and $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{Zr}_{2-y}\text{Nb}_y\text{O}_7$ were studied by X-ray powder diffraction technique in order to investigate limits on the possibilities of ionic substitution (limiting radius ratio). Here it is observed that radius ratio criterion seems to be relatively unimportant in determining the stability limit for pyrochlore structure.

Pyrochlore compounds in which substitution of cations taking place either at A or B sites have been reported by various workers²⁻¹¹. Pyrochlore structure has the general formula $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ where A ions retain the eightfold co-ordination while B ions are only in sixfold co-ordination. Thus A ion is larger than B ion in the pyrochlore structure. The pyrochlore space group is found to be $\text{Fd}3\text{M}-\text{O}_h^7$ and there are eight $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ formula units in the pyrochlore unit cell.

All the compositions mentioned in Table I were prepared by using standard ceramic technique and X-ray diffractometer patterns were taken on Philips X-ray machine using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation with Nickel filter. The results of X-ray analysis are given in Table I.

From Table I it is observed that in the systems investigated, the single pyrochlore phase is observed up to the compositions $\text{Y}_{1.6}\text{Ca}_{0.4}\text{Ti}_{1.6}\text{Nb}_{0.4}\text{O}_7$, $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{1.2}\text{Zr}_{0.8}\text{Nb}_{1.2}\text{O}_7$ and $\text{La}_{1.4}\text{Sr}_{0.6}\text{Zr}_{1.4}\text{Nb}_{0.6}\text{O}_7$. Knop *et al*⁶ while studying pyrochlore titanates of the type $\text{Y}_{2-x}\text{Ln}_x\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_7$ (where Ln = lanthanide ion from Sm to Lu) have observed the stability limit extending from Ahrens radius ratio of nearly 1.22 to 1.50. In the case of pyrochlore Stannates⁷ they have reported the lower limit of $[r(\text{A}^{3+})/r(\text{Sn}^{4+})]$ 1.19 (Ahrens) and upper limit